

Synthesis, characterization and single crystal X-ray structures of 2-pyridyl bis(pyrazineamino)methane and bis[2-pyridyl(pyrazineamino)methanolato]cobalt(III) perchlorate : A consequence of cobalt ion-assisted oxidative deamination of 2-pyridyl bis(pyrazineamino)methane

Umasankar Ray^{a,c*}, Abhijit Pal^b and Rajarshi Ghosh^{b*}

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Chung-Yuan Christian University, Chung Li, Taiwan, ROC

E-mail : usray_chem@yahoo.co.in

^bDepartment of Chemistry, Burdwan University, Golapbag, Burdwan-713 104, West Bengal, India

E-mail : rajarshi_chem@yahoo.co.in

^cPresently at : Department of Chemistry, BCARE Institute of Management & Technology, Kanfala, Murshidabad-742 184, West Bengal, India

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Abstract : A new Schiff base, 2-pyridyl bis(pyrazineamino)methane (L_1) has been synthesized and characterized by elemental analysis, spectroscopic investigations and single crystal X-ray diffraction measurements. Reaction of cobalt(II) perchlorate hexahydrate with two molar equivalents of L_1 under ambient conditions resulted concurrent oxidation of divalent Co^{II} metal ion with oxygenation and deamination of the amination polydentate ligand to produce bis[2-pyridyl(pyrazineamino)methanolato]cobalt(III) perchlorate trihydrate designated as $[Co(L_2)]ClO_4 \cdot 3H_2O$ (**1**). The complex **1** is also characterized by spectroscopy, elemental analysis and X-ray crystallography. X-Ray crystal structure of the complex cation, $[Co(L_2)_2]^+$, shows that the two L_2 ligands are coordinated to the central cobalt(III) metal ion in a facial mode to afford a slightly distorted octahedral geometry. The two pyridyl and two pyrazine N atoms constitute the equatorial plane on which the cobalt(III) ion lies whereas methanolate O atoms occupy the axial positions.

Keywords : Co^{III} complex, pyridine, pyrazine, Schiff base, X-ray structure.

Introduction

Low-spin cobalt(III) complexes are important because of its kinetic inertness, which has facilitated mechanistic studies in coordination chemistry. Generally, all octahedral cobalt(III) complexes are diamagnetic, except $[CoF_6]^{3-}$ and $[CoF_3(H_2O)_3]^1$. Co^{III} is usually obtained from Co^{II} by atmospheric or chemical oxidation. Cobalt is one of the essential trace elements for animals, including humans, because it is incorporated into the vitamin B_{12} molecule. In the form of vitamin B_{12} (cobalamin), this metal plays a number of crucial roles in many biological functions. It can act as an electron carrier at biochemical redox centre, because of its availability of two readily accessible stable oxidation states (+2 and +3). Moreover, it is well known that Schiff base and its complexes were proposed as a model molecule for vitamin B_{12} ². Besides this, cobalt-Schiff base complexes have the mag-

netic, catalytic and biological activity³⁻⁶. Many Schiff base ligands containing one heterocycle have been appeared in literature⁷ but Schiff base ligands containing two different heterocycle units are very few⁸. We have designed and synthesized a new Schiff base (2-pyridyl)bis(pyrazineamino)methane (L_1) that contains two heterocycles viz. pyridine and pyrazine units. Two molar equivalents of L_1 reacts with $Co(ClO_4)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ in EtOH in the presence of molecular oxygen to form bis[2-pyridyl(pyrazineamino)methanolato]cobalt(III) perchlorate trihydrate (**1**). The synthesis, characterization and single crystal X-ray structures of L_1 and the complex **1** are reported herein.

Results and discussion

Synthesis :

The new Schiff base ligand L_1 was synthesized in

high yield by Schiff base condensation of 2-aminopyrazine with 2-pyridylaldehyde in refluxing solvent (Scheme 1). Elemental analysis, IR, MS spectrum and X-ray crystal structure are consistent with the formulation of the ligand. The complex (**1**) was synthesized by reaction of $\text{Co}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ with two molar equivalents of (2-pyridyl)-bis(pyrazineamino)methane (L_1) in EtOH in the presence of molecular oxygen in refluxing condition for 30 min. A plausible mechanism of formation of **1** from the reaction between L_1 and Co^{II} salt has been proposed⁹ in Scheme 1.

112.64(13)°. The bond lengths of N1-C1 and N5-C5 are 1.439 and 1.457 Å, respectively. Two pyrazine rings are not co-planar having dihedral angle of 79.59°. The dihedral angles between the plan 1 (C6, C7, C8, C9, C10, N4) and plan 2 (C1, C2, N2, C3, C4, N3) is 56.90° and between plan 1 and plan 3 (C11, C12, N7, C13, C14, N6) is 72.40°. Intermolecular hydrogen bonding between N-H...N(pyrazine) [H...N, 2.16 (Å); $\angle\text{N-H}\cdots\text{N} = 173.81^\circ$] and C-H(pyrazine)...N(pyrazine) [H...N, 2.70 (Å); $\angle\text{C-H}\cdots\text{N} = 156.54^\circ$] exists in L_1 (Fig. 2). Weak π - π interaction (3.782(1) Å) is also observed between

Scheme 1. Proposed mechanism.

Crystal structure :

X-Ray structure of (2-pyridyl)bis(pyrazineamino)-methane (L_1) :

The structure of L_1 was determined by X-ray crystallography and is shown in Fig. 1. The selected bond distances and angles are listed in Table 1. The geometry around the central carbon atom (C5) is distorted tetrahedral with the bond angle ranges from 107.7(9) to

the pyridine moieties of one molecule with another. The typical cutoff distance for π - π stacking interactions is 3.9 Å¹⁰.

X-Ray structure of complex **1** :

The structure of complex **1** is shown in Fig. 3. Selected bond distances and angles are listed in Table 1. The co-complex consists of one cobalt(III) ion, two deprotonated ligands L_2^- forming a complex cation,

Fig. 1. Single crystal X-ray structure of ligand L_1 .

Table 1. Selected bond distances (Å) and bond angles ($^\circ$) for L_1 and **1**

Distance	(Å)	Angle	($^\circ$)
Ligand (L_1):			
N1-C1	1.361(2)	\angle N1-C5-N5	109.97(14)
N1-C5	1.439(2)	\angle N1-C5-C6	109.33(13)
C5-C6	1.518(2)	\angle N5-C5-C6	112.64(13)
C5-H5	0.972(17)	\angle N1-C5-H5	107.7(9)
		\angle N5-C5-H5	109.1(9)
		\angle C6-C5-H5	108.0(9)
Complex 1 :			
Co-O2	1.886(2)	\angle O2-Co2-O2'	180.0
Co-O2'	1.886(2)	\angle N5-Co2-N5'	180.0
Co-N5	1.917(3)	\angle N6-Co2-N6'	180.0
Co-N5'	1.917(3)	\angle N5-Co2-N6	90.66(12)
Co-N6'	1.975(3)	\angle N5-Co2-N6'	89.34(12)
Co-N6	1.975(3)	\angle O2-Co2-N6	88.02(11)
		\angle O2-Co2-N6'	91.98(11)
		\angle O2-Co2-N5	84.91(12)
		\angle O2-Co2-N5'	95.09(13)

$[\text{Co}(L_2)_2]^+$, and a disordered perchlorate counter-anion. The crystal structure of cation shows two tridentate (2-pyridyl)(pyrazineamino)methanolate (L_2) ligands coordinated facially to the cobalt(III) ion to form a slightly distorted octahedral geometry. The two pyridyl and two pyrazine N atoms constitute the equatorial plane on which the cobalt(III) ion lies, the methanolate O atoms occupy the axial positions. The distance of Co-O (1.886(2) Å) is shorter than those of Co-N5 (1.917(3) Å) and Co-N6 (1.975(3) Å) (Table 1) that may be due to the better overlapping between two hard centers [Co^{III} and oxygen].

Fig. 2. Hydrogen bonding between N-H---N (pyrazine) and C-H---N (pyrazine)---N (pyrazine)

Table 2. Crystal data and structure refinement parameters for L_1 and **1**

Compound	L_1	1
Formula	$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_7$	$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{24}\text{ClCoN}_8\text{O}_9$
F_w	279.31	614.85
Crystal system	Monoclinic	Triclinic
Space group	P_21/C	P_1
a (Å)	11.7573(17)	9.0885(10)
b (Å)	12.8069(17)	12.2620(15)
c (Å)	9.9854(19)	12.5611(12)
α ($^\circ$)	90	107.905(8)
β ($^\circ$)	113.867(11)	108.312(10)
γ ($^\circ$)	90	94.104(11)
V (Å ³)	1375.0(4)	1242.5(2)
Z	4	2
d_{calc} (g/cm ³)	1.349	1.643
$F(000)$	584	632
μ (Mo K_α) (mm ⁻¹)	0.089	0.866
Range (2θ) for data collection ($^\circ$)	$3.78 \leq 2\theta \leq 49.96$	$4.10 \leq 2\theta \leq 50.00$
Data/restraints/parameters	2418/0/243	4241/0/391
Quality-of-fit indicator ^c	1.057	1.038
Final R indices	$R_1 = 0.0385$,	$R_1 = 0.0468$,
$[I > 2\sigma(I)]^{a,b}$	$wR_2 = 0.0994$	$wR_2 = 0.1163$
R indices (all data)	$R_1 = 0.0590$,	$R_1 = 0.0651$,
	$wR_2 = 0.1102$	$wR_2 = 0.1271$
^a $R_1 = \sum F_o - F_c / \sum F_o $. ^b $wR_2 = [\sum w(F_o^2 - F_c^2)^2 / \sum w(F_o^2)^2]^{1/2}$. $w = 1 / [\sigma^2(F_o^2) + (ap)^2 + (bp)]$, $p = [\max(F_o^2 \text{ or } 0) + 2(F_c^2)] / 3$. $a = 0.0567$, $b = 0.1029$ for L_1 , $a = 0.0628$, $b = 1.2405$ for 1 . ^c quality-of-fit = $[\sum w(F_o^2 - F_c^2)^2 / (N_{\text{observed}} - N_{\text{parameters}})]^{1/2}$.		

Fig. 3. Single crystal X-ray structure of complex 1.

The molecule has a center of symmetry through the cobalt(III) ion. The dihedral angles of plan 1 (N5, N5A, N6, N6A) to plan 2 (O2, O2A, N5, N5A), plan 1 to plan 3 (O2, O2A, N6, N6A) and plan 2 to plan 3 are 87.96°, 84.89° and 89.17° respectively, so the coordination octahedron is slightly distorted. Both ligands bend into a saddle structure. The two pyridyl and pyrazinyl rings are co-planar to each other having dihedral angle of 0° while the dihedral angle between the pyrazinyl and pyridyl ring is 69.58°. The molecules look like are a pair of scissors (Fig. 4). No π - π interaction is observed in the molecule.

Fig. 4. Scissors like structure of complex 1.

Spectral studies :

Infrared spectrum of L_1 shows a sharp absorption at 3356 cm^{-1} that corresponds to the presence of NH (secondary amine). The bands appeared at 3011–3202 and

1589 cm^{-1} are due to -C-H stretching vibration and C=N vibration, respectively. IR spectra of complex 1 shows a broad band at 3320 cm^{-1} which corresponds to $\nu(-\text{NH})$. The bands appeared at 1543 cm^{-1} is due to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$. The uncoordinated perchlorate ion is characterized by an intense and broad absorption centred around 1088 cm^{-1} and a moderate and sharp band at 625 cm^{-1} ¹¹.

Solution electronic spectra of complex 1 shows weak transition at 500 nm ($\epsilon = 80 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) is due to d-d transition. Moderate intense peaks at 336 nm ($\epsilon = 2608 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) may assign to ligand to metal charge transfer transitions¹². Two intense transitions observed 235 nm (17000 $\text{M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) and 209 nm (15478 $\text{M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) are due to intraligand π - π^* transitions.

Experimental

Materials :

2-Aminopyrazine, 2-pyridinecarboxaldehyde, $\text{Co}(\text{ClO}_4) \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ were purchased from Aldrich Chemical Co. All the reagents were used as received. Solvents were used after drying with appropriate reagents.

CAUTION : *Perchlorate salts are dangerous (especially if they are dry) and should be handled with care!*

Physical measurements :

IR spectra were obtained from a JASCO FT/IR-460 plus spectrometer. Elemental analyses were obtained from PE 2400 series II CHNS/O analyzer. NMR spectra were measured on a Bruker Avance 300 MHz spectrometer. UV-Vis spectra were recorded on Shimadzu UV-2450 spectrophotometer. Mass spectra were recorded on Shimadzu GCMS-QP2010S spectrometer.

Synthesis of ligand (2-pyridyl)bis(pyrazineamino)-methane (L_1) :

To a refluxing solution of 2-aminopyrazine (0.02 mol, 1.90 g) in minimum ethanol (95%), 2-pyridylaldehyde (0.01 mol, 1.07 g) was added and refluxed for 8 h. The resultant yellowish-brown solution was allowed to cool slowly to room temperature. The colorless crystals formed were isolated by filtration and washed with ice-cold ethanol (95%, 10 ml). A second crop was obtained by further slow evaporation of the filtrate at room temperature. Yield 1.53 g (58%) (Found : C, 59.86; N, 35.16; H, 4.75. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_7$: C, 60.20; N, 35.10; H, 4.69%); EI-MS : m/z 279 (M^+); IR (KBr disk cm^{-1}) : $\nu_{\text{N-H}}$ 3382, $\nu_{\text{C-N}}$ 1589.

Synthesis of bis[2-pyridyl(pyrazineamino)methanolato]cobalt(III) perchlorate [Co(L₂)₂]ClO₄·3H₂O (1) :

Co(ClO₄)₂·6H₂O (0.092 g, 0.25 mmol) was added to a solution of L₁ (0.139 g, 0.50 mmol) in ethanol (15 ml); a pink-red solution formed immediately and progressively darkened over time with reflux for 30 min. After that the solution was filtered and kept at room temperature for slow evaporation, bright pink-red block-shaped crystals were deposited after one week. The crystals were washed with ice-cold ethanol and dried in air (yield 65 %) (Found : C, 39.37; N, 18.46; H, 3.40. Calcd. for C₂₀H₂₄ClCoN₈O₉ : C, 39.07; N, 18.22; H, 3.93 %); IR (KBr disk cm⁻¹) : ν(N-H) 3387; ν(C-N) 1543; ν(ClO₄) 1088 and 624.

X-Ray crystallography :

The diffraction data of L₁ and 1 were collected on Bruker AXS P4 diffractometer¹³ at 22 °C and which was equipped with graphite-monochromated Mo Kα (k_a = 0.71073 Å) radiation. Data reduction was carried by standard methods with the use of well-established computational procedures¹⁴. The structure factors were obtained after Lorentz and polarization correction. Empirical absorption correction based on “ω-scan” was applied for compound L₁ and 1. The atoms were found in a series of alternating difference Fourier maps and least-square refinements. The structures were solved by the direct method and refined by full matrix least squares calculations (SHELXL-97)¹⁵. Basic information concerned to crystal parameters and structure refinement is summarized in Table 2.

Conclusions :

A new Schiff base ligand, 2-pyridyl bis(pyrazine-amino)methane (L₁) has been synthesized and structurally characterized. Reaction of Co(ClO₄)₂·6H₂O with two molar equivalents of L₁ under ambient conditions resulted concurrent oxidation of divalent Co^{II} metal ion with oxygenation and deamination of L₁ to form bis[2-pyridyl(pyrazineamino)methanolato]cobalt(III) perchlorate, trihydrate [Co(L₂)₂]ClO₄·3H₂O (1). The complex 1 is characterized by IR, EA, UV-Vis spectroscopy. The structure was confirmed by X-ray crystallography. X-Ray crystal structure of the complex cation, [Co(L₂)₂]⁺, shows that the two L₂ ligands are coordinated to the central cobalt(III) metal ion in a facial mode to afford a slightly distorted octahedral geometry.

Supplementary material :

CCDC Nos. 892119 and 892120 contain the supplementary crystallographic data for L₁ and 1, respectively. These data can be obtained free of charge via www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk/conts/retrieving.html, or from the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre, 12 Union Road, Cambridge CB2 1EZ, UK; Fax : 44-1223-336033; or E-mail : deposit@ccdc.cam.ac.uk.

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